

Analytical Report

Sample data report

New Mexico Bureau of Geology
and Mineral Resources

801 Leroy Place
Socorro, NM 87801
(575) 835-5160
(575) 835-5416

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1350	uS/cm	1		12/16/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		12/19/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	76.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	12/17/2019
Iron	0.290	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	12/17/2019
Magnesium	24.7	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	12/17/2019
Potassium	12.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	12/17/2019
Silicon	15.3	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	12/17/2019
Sodium	187	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	12/17/2019
Strontium	1.27	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	12/17/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0973	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Arsenic	0.0044	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Barium	0.057	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	1/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Boron 11	0.186	mg/L	5	0.005	(0.025)	1/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Lithium	0.064	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Manganese	0.816	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Silicon	15.7	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	1/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Strontium	1.32	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Uranium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Vanadium	0.0027	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Chloride	153	mg/L	5	1 (5)	12/17/2019
Fluoride	1.85	mg/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Nitrate	0.12	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	12/17/2019
Sulfate	213	mg/L	5	1 (5)	12/17/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
-----------	--------	-------	----------	-----------------	---------------

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Alkalinity as CaCO3	310	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	378	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	15.04	meq/L	1		
Cations total	14.30	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.55	%	1		
SiO2	33.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	893	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-01	Customer sample ID: SS 1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	292	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	----------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3800	uS/cm	1		12/16/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	----------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	7.9	ph Units	1		12/19/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	----------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	232	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	12/17/2019
Magnesium	83.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Potassium	22.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Silicon	16.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	12/17/2019
Sodium	574	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Strontium	4.20	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	12/17/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	----------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0597	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Barium	0.016	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	1/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Boron 11	0.447	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	1/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lithium	0.174	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Manganese	0.005	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Silicon	16.4	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	1/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Strontium	4.17	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Uranium	0.0104	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Vanadium	0.0063	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
---	-------------------------------------	------------------------------	-----------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.26	mg/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Chloride	770	mg/L	10	1 (10)	12/17/2019
Fluoride	1.43	mg/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Nitrate	3.12	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	12/17/2019
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	12/17/2019
Sulfate	779	mg/L	10	1 (10)	12/17/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
---	-------------------------------------	----------------------------	-----------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	283	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	345	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	----------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	43.71	meq/L	1		
Cations total	43.98	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.31	%	1		
SiO2	35.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2680	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-02	Customer sample ID: ESS 1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	----------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	923	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3160	uS/cm	1		12/16/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	---------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		12/19/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	172	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	12/17/2019
Magnesium	76.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Silicon	8.46	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	12/17/2019
Sodium	424	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Strontium	3.28	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	12/17/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0068	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	1/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Boron 11	0.359	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	1/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lithium	0.145	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Silicon	7.98	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	1/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0113	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	---------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	12/18/2019
Fluoride	1.45	mg/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Nitrate	0.45	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	12/18/2019
Sulfate	645	mg/L	10	1 (10)	12/18/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	---------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	279	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	---------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.88	meq/L	1		
Cations total	33.84	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.93	%	1		
SiO2	17.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2130	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-03	Customer sample ID: GS 1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	---------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	747	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
--	----------------------------------	-----------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3180	uS/cm	1		12/16/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
--	----------------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		12/19/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
--	----------------------------------	--------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	165	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	12/17/2019
Magnesium	77.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Potassium	19.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Silicon	8.76	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	12/17/2019
Sodium	439	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	12/17/2019
Strontium	3.28	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	12/17/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
--	----------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0328	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	1/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Boron 11	0.365	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	1/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	1/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lithium	0.147	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Silicon	8.41	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	1/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Strontium	3.41	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	1/3/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0046	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	1/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
--	----------------------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	12/18/2019
Fluoride	1.39	mg/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Nitrate	0.19	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	12/18/2019
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	12/18/2019
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	12/18/2019

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
--	----------------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	211	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	249	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	12/19/2019

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 191206
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 12/13/2019 12:50:41 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
--	----------------------------------	-----------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.60	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.18	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.03	%	1		
SiO2	18.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2130	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 191206-04	Customer sample ID: SSS 1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
--	----------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-------------------------

Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	732	mg CaCO3/ L	1		